

1 **Strategies in IBD targeting the leukotriene receptors: Cyslr1.**

2 Pre-Clinical/Clinical/Translational/Phase1-3
3 Compassionate Use Document (FDA format)

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8 1. The concept presented and being tested here: use and experimental clinical testing of a
9 monoclonal antibody targeting the cysteine leukotriene receptors.

10 a. Here, we propose pharmacologic antagonism of Cyslr1.

11 2. Rationale: Current therapeutic targeting strategies in Crohn's Disease include approaches
12 focused on the cytokines TNF-alpha, IL-17, and IL-23. Targeted oral therapies include the mesalamine
13 agents that have a broad spectrum function with at least partial prostaglandin coverage, while the other
14 major FDA approved orally approved therapies for IBD, the Jak kinase inhibitors, target the JAK/STAT
15 hematopoietic cytokine signaling pathways, not eicosanoid based inflammatory mediated processes.

16 3. Therapeutic targeting strategies are limited.

17 4. We used a systems biologic approach to discovery of genes with putative functions in propagation
18 of inflammation in the gastrointestinal tract.

19 5. We identified multiple genes of the cysteine inflammatory receptor family and the cysteine
20 leukotriene receptors as candidate molecules for clinical intervention in IBD/Crohn's Disease.

21 6. Compassionate Use, also known as Expanded Access, provides access to an investigational
22 therapeutic (drug) when a life threatening condition exists and no comparable medication is available for
23 treatment.

24 7. The major requirements for Compassionate Use are:

25 a. The patient or patients has/have a life-threatening disease or medical condition.

26 b. There is no comparable or satisfactory alternative therapy

27 c. The potential benefit outweighs the potential risks

28 d. The use does not interfere with initiation, conduct or completion of clinical investigations.

1. Some significant fraction of patients who develop resistance to anti-TNF agents will experience an
unsafe and rapid deterioration in disease status, that features in some patients life-threatening restriction
to oral access resulting from obstruction or structure.

9. It is estimated that on average 99% of Expanded Access (Compassionate Use) are approved by
the FDA (Food and Drug Administration).

The following text remains to be edited:

10. We used cells from healthy individuals and authentic tissues from affected patient cohorts,
measuring total transcription in response to blockade of TNF-alpha or in response to exposure to the
TNF-alpha cytokine to study mechanisms controlling resistance to clinical interventions (therapy) using
TNF-alpha inhibition in humans.

a. Model systems were used only to conceptualize systems biologic concepts and provide information
regarding minimal components within an immunologic network.

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3 11. The transcriptome-wide analysis also included discovery of individual gene targets likely to
function in conferring resistance to first-line biologic agents in gastroenterology.

4 12. For this approach, we measured total transcription using microarray in patient cells and tissues
resistant to infliximab or another biologic targeting TNF-alpha.

- 5 a. In this proposal, we focus on resistance to TNFa inhibition by agents like infliximab, etanercept,
6 adalimumab or golimumab.
7 b. Resistance to biological targeting IL-23 like guselkumab is less well understood and addressed
separately.

8 13. We integrated findings from measurements of total transcription in separate cellular systems to
9 produce a concise and accurate biological description of cytokine interconnectedness and feedback
mechanisms in immunologic signaling.

10 14. We identified an inflammation propagating disease process involving cell to tissue communication
between the gut and the hematopoietic compartment in humans with established (diagnosed) disease.

- 11 a. Here, we propose the use of oral 5-ASA mesalamine agents (e.g., Pentasa), normally reserved for
12 patients with mild or moderate disease, to limit putative activation of systemic disease resulting
from inflammatory signaling derived from the gut, to which blood cells are exposed to.
13 b. This should occur concurrent with infliximab administration.

14 15. We pioneered the concept of a hematopoietic phenotype in humans with Crohn's Disease, one
that is highly responsive to disease activity, a phenotype we propose complicates understanding of
15 induction and maintenance of remission in humans with Crohn's Disease treatment with infliximab or
golimumab.

- 16 a. Here we propose that it follows that basic treatment of the hematopoietic compartment with a broad
17 spectrum inflammatory, like orally available JAK kinase inhibitors, will thus function to support or
enhance responsiveness to intravenous TNFa inhibition.

18 16. Thus, the formulation here proposes for the use of a selective JAK1 inhibitor (upadacitinib (Rinvoq))
19 combined with a eicasanoid-targeting 5-ASA mesalamine agent (Pentasa, Asacol) in patients being
20 treated with infliximab for severe Crohn's Disease.
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Scavenger receptors and inflammatory signaling in active Crohn's Disease.

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Scavenger receptors

- Scarf1
- Haptoglobin

Cysteine:

- Cystm1 activation
- Csnrp1 induction
- CBS activation
- Crisp3
- Crispld3
- Csrp2

Citations

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